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Introduction

Invasive coronary angiography (ICA) and transthoracic echocardiography (TTE) are cornerstone imaging modalities in cardiology, essential for diagnosis, treatment and follow-up in patients with coronary artery disease (CAD).^{1,2} Both procedures result in detailed reports, typically recorded in a semi-structured free text format within electronic health records (EHRs). While this format enables flexible, context-rich documentation, standardization is limited, restricting its usability for data-driven research, clinical decision support systems and artificial intelligence (AI) applications.^{3,4,5}

The absence of structured labels presents a critical bottleneck in AI-driven research, where large, accurately annotated datasets are essential for the development of robust models.⁶ Manual annotation remains the predominant method for dataset creation, yet it is laborintensive and prone to human error, making it impractical for large-scale supervised learning.⁷ As a result, much of the valuable data generated in clinical practice remains inaccessible.⁸

Recent advances in natural language processing (NLP), particularly the emergence of large language models (LLMs), offer new opportunities for automating the extraction of structured information from free-text reports.⁹ These models, built on transformer-based architectures with attention mechanisms, have demonstrated superior contextual understanding and scalability compared to earlier NLP techniques.¹⁰ LLMs have already shown promise in automating structured data extraction from free-text radiology reports.^{6,11}

We hypothesize that LLM-based methods can automate the structured classification of ICA and TTE reports, enabling scalable dataset creation for AI applications and secondary data use. These methods also offer a robust foundation for extracting standardized data elements required for clinical registries, quality improvement programs and mandatory health system reporting, thereby reducing administrative burden, enhancing data completeness and supporting data-driven oversight across diverse healthcare settings. In this study, two distinct LLM-based approaches, prompt engineering and fine-tuning, were developed and evaluated using free-text cardiology reports obtained from routine clinical practice. In prompt engineering, task instructions, optionally with several examples, guide a pretrained

1 model without changing its parameters. In fine-tuning, the model's weights are updated
2 based

3
4 Figure 1: a) Prompt engineering method, resulting in an optimized prompt, where no model
5 training takes place. b) Fine-tuning method, a pre-trained LLM is trained on a domain specific
6 dataset, where adjusting the weights of the network results in a fine-tuned model. on labeled
7 data to adjust to the target task.^{12,13,14} A brief schematic comparing prompt engineering and
8 fine-tuning is provided in Figure 1. Their classification performance and implementation
9 complexity were systematically compared.

10 Methods

11 Datasets

12 A comprehensive pseudo-anonymized database was constructed from the EHRs of patients
13 treated for acute coronary syndrome (ACS) at Leiden University Medical Center (LUMC), The
14 Netherlands, between 2010 and 2024. This database encompassed all clinical data generated
15 during initial treatment and subsequent follow-up of these patients. The study protocol
16 (nWMODIV2_2022006) was approved by the institutional review board of LUMC, which

1 waived the requirement for obtaining informed consent for the use of data from individual
2 patients. All procedures were conducted in accordance with institutional guidelines and
3 regulations. From the source database, two study-specific datasets were created by random
4 sampling: one consisting of 1000 ICA reports and the other comprising 1000 TTE reports.
5 All reports were written in Dutch, adhered to a semi-structured format and were composed
6 by board-certified cardiologists during routine clinical care. None of the reports contained
7 personally identifiable information, apart from clinical details specific to the modality. Only
8 the textual content of the reports, without any accompanying metadata, was processed
9 through the LLMs. Data processing and model inference were performed within secure,
10 encrypted environments compliant with European data protection regulations, using only
11 anonymized reports that underwent manual review for the presence of personally
12 identifiable data prior to processing. Textual data was pre-processed to enhance quality and
13 consistency prior to model training. Automated cleaning scripts based on regular
14 expressions, a technique for identifying and modifying text patterns, were used to remove
15 unnecessary spaces, redundant line breaks and formatting artifacts introduced during data
16 extraction. This process reduced noise, corrected structural inconsistencies and
17 standardized the text format across all reports, which were written and transferred to
18 different data formats (finally to the XML standard) by different software packages used in
19 the hospital over the years.

20 **Data labeling**

21 A structured annotation protocol was employed, involving two independent expert
22 reviewers who each annotated all 2,000 reports across two iterative rounds. Prior to the first
23 round, detailed annotation guidelines were established and subsequently refined after each
24 iteration to improve label consistency and annotation accuracy. Final labels were determined
25 by resolving any disagreements through consensus discussions between the annotators.

26 To assess the difficulty of the labeling task and establish a baseline for evaluating the
27 LLM performance, average manual annotation scores were calculated. These scores were
28 derived by comparing each annotator's final-round labels with the agreed-upon consensus
29 labels.

1 ICA reports were labeled for attributes relevant to diagnosis and treatment decisions:
 2 presence of acute occlusion, presence of bypass grafts, presence of significant epicardial
 3 coronary artery disease (CAD), treatment strategy (PCI, referral for coronary artery bypass
 4 grafting (CABG), or medical treatment only), and identification of culprit vessel(s), with
 5 labels assigned for both the main coronary artery (Main) and specific branch/segment (Sub).

Label	Values
ICA dataset	
Occlusion	Yes, no
No CAD	Yes, no
Graft	Yes, no
Treatment strategy	PCI, CABG, medical
Main	RDA, RCA, RCx, LM, Graft, IM, no
Sub	RDA, RCA, RCx, LM, Graft, IM, AL, D, MO, PL, RDP, RV, S, no
TTE dataset	
LV function	Normal, mildly, moderately or severely reduced, no data
Valve dysfunction type	None, stenosis, regurgitation, both, no data
Valve dysfunction grade	None, mild, moderate, severe, no data

7 Table 1: Overview of the possible ICA and TTE labels

8 A “no culprit” label was used when no culprit could be identified. Multiple labels were
 9 permitted only for the culprit-vessel category (e.g., RCA/RDA); all other categories were
 10 single-label. TTE reports were labeled for left ventricular (LV) systolic function and valvular
 11 dysfunction, including the type and severity for each cardiac valve (aortic (AV), mitral (MV),
 12 tricuspid (TV) and pulmonary (PV)), using guideline-consistent ordered categories: LV
 13 function was categorized as normal, mildly, moderately, or severely reduced, and valvular
 14 stenosis/regurgitation as none, mild, moderate, or severe.^{15,16} When multiple gradings were
 15 present within a report, the most severe category was selected. A “no data” label was
 16 assigned when relevant findings were absent from the report. A complete overview of all
 17 label categories is provided in Table 1.

18 Data availability

19 The data underlying this article cannot be shared publicly due to the privacy of participants
 20 in the study.

1

2 **LLM assessment**

3 Both fine-tuning and prompt engineering (see Figure 1) were tested on a commercially
4 available LLM (GPT-4o via Azure OpenAI) and several open-source state-of-the-art (SOTA)
5 models available via Huggingface.co and Ollama.com that can be used on-site. Open-source
6 SOTA models were selected by identifying the two most popular models for text classification
7 or feature extraction across three categories: general-purpose, medical domain-specific and
8 multilingual LLMs. For on-site prompt engineering two different hardware constraints are
9 tested. A smaller local GPU of 16Gb, which would be an average laptop GPU and a bigger high
10 performance cluster (HPC) GPU of 48Gb. For on-site fine-tuning only the HPC hardware was
11 tested, since hardware requirements for fine-tuning are too large for small GPUs. Selection
12 was done with the important constraint that the model could either be run i) locally on a
13 16Gb GPU for local prompt engineering or ii) on a 48Gb GPU for HPC prompt engineering or
14 iii) be trained on a 48Gb GPU for fine-tuning.

15 **Fine-tuning**

16 For on-site fine-tuning each model was extended with a classification layer, such that the
17 model directly outputs class indexes. This classification layer was trained without
18 pretraining, while the underlying model was fine-tuned on the manually labeled ICA and TTE
19 datasets. To mitigate overfitting, we implemented early stopping based on the performance
20 on the validation set, along with weight decay as a regularization technique. Additionally, the
21 learning rate, a crucial hyperparameter, is fine-tuned to optimize performance while
22 maintaining stability. For on-site finetuning the following pre-trained models were selected
23 from Huggingface.co on March 2, 2025: multilingual-e5-large from Intfloat¹⁷ (multilingual 1),
24 bert-base-multilingual-uncased-sentiment from NLPTown (multilingual 2),
25 BiomedVLPBioVil-T from Microsoft¹⁸ (medical 1), MedCPT-Cross-Encoder from NCBI¹⁹
26 (medical 2), bart-base from Facebook²⁰ (general 1) and ms-marco-MiniLM-L-6-v2 from
27 Cross-encoder (general 2).

28 Fine-tuning of the commercially available GPT-4o model was performed using the Azure
29 OpenAI fine-tuning API. The model was adapted to the classification tasks using manually

1 labeled reports. The fine-tuning process is subjected to predefined limitations inherent to
2 the commercial API, which permits adjustment of only a single relevant hyperparameter; the
3 learning rate multiplier. Modification of the model architecture or implementation of training
4 optimizations such as early stopping or weight regularization are not possible. The optimal
5 learning rate was selected based on validation performance and training stability, ensuring
6 generalization to unseen data. Because fine-tuning was performed on OpenAI servers, the
7 resulting model weights are not accessible to the authors and therefore cannot be shared.

8 **Prompt Engineering**

9 Prompt-based inference was conducted using a few-shot prompting strategy. Each clinical
10 report was combined with standardized labeling instructions to create a structured input
11 format. Prompts were category-specific, with one call per label. Structured output templates
12 (JSON schemas) were used to ensure consistency and facilitate accurate parsing. Prompts
13 were iteratively refined on a subset of the training data, with adjustments to wording and
14 structure aimed at minimizing misclassification and improving labeling accuracy. Model
15 settings were configured to promote consistent outputs, with parameter settings to minimize
16 variability during output generation. For local prompt engineering, the following small
17 pretrained models were selected from Ollama.com on March 2, 2025: Aya 23 from Cohere²¹
18 (multilingual 1), Llama3.2 from Meta (multilingual 2), MedLlama2 by Sourcell (medical 1),
19 Phi-4 from Microsoft (general 1) and Gemma3 from Google (general 2/multilingual). No
20 second medical model was selected because a decent medical runner up model was not
21 available at this moment. For HPC prompt engineering the following larger pre-trained
22 models were selected from Ollama.com on March 2, 2025: Gemma3 from Google
23 (multilingual 1) and Wizardlm2 from Microsoft (multilingual 2), Meditron (medical 1)²²,
24 Medllama2 by Sourcell
25 (medical 2), Deepseek-R1-Distill-Qwen from DeepSeek (general 1) and Phi-4 from Microsoft
26 (general 2). For some models larger versions exist, the largest version that can fit on either
27 the local GPU (16GB) or the HPC cluster GPU (48GB) was chosen.

1 **Analysis**

2 Both data sets were randomly divided into a training and a test set, at patient level, with a
3 ratio of 70:30. For the prompt engineering method, the training set was used for prompt
4 optimization and example selection. For the fine-tuning method, the training set was again
5 split, at patient level, in a training and validation set with a ratio of 85:15. The training set
6 was used to fine-tune the models, while the validation set is used to monitor overfitting. For
7 all on-site model comparisons a 5-fold cross-validation scheme was used. Model evaluation
8 was done by calculating metrics on the combined predictions on all validation sets, which
9 aggregate to the whole training set. The test set, which remains completely unseen during
10 prompt optimization and fine-tuning, was reserved for final performance evaluation. Models
11 were evaluated using the following performance metrics: accuracy, average recall and
12 macroaveraged F1-score. For the multi-class multi-label tasks (main and sub culprit vessel)
13 a strict evaluation criterion was adopted: classification outputs were only considered correct
14 if the entire set of predicted labels per report exactly matched the reference labels.
15 Consequently, partially correct classifications, such as predicting “RDA/D” when only “D” was
16 correct, were seen as incorrect. To quantify variability, 95% confidence intervals were
17 estimated using 1000 bootstrap iterations for each metric. To assess statistically significant
18 differences in performance, the Bonferroni corrected p-value (p_b) is calculated per label
19 category, using the best-performing model as the reference for all pairwise comparisons.
20 Finally, misclassified cases from the test set were manually reviewed to identify recurring
21 patterns and potential sources of model error.

22 **Results**

23 **Study population**

24 Both datasets comprised 1000 unique reports. In the ICA dataset, each report represented a
25 unique patient ($n = 1000$), while in the TTE dataset, the reports corresponded to 736 unique
26 patients, with 264 patients contributing two reports each. No reports were duplicated and
27 no patient appeared more than twice within the TTE dataset. The mean age of the patients
28 was 65.7 ± 11.9 years in the ICA cohort and 62.2 ± 11.2 years in the TTE cohort. The sex
29 distribution in the ICA dataset was 70.7% male ($n = 707$) and 29.3% female ($n = 293$). In the

1 TTE dataset, 74.6% were male (n = 746) and 25.4% were female (n = 254). The initial clinical
2 presentation among patients in the ICA dataset was ST-segment elevation myocardial
3 infarction (STEMI) in 33.1% (n = 331) , non-ST-segment elevation myocardial infarction
4 (NSTEMI) in 30.7% (n = 307) and unstable angina in 36.2% (n = 362). In the TTE dataset,
5 66.2% (n = 487) of cases presented with STEMI, 25.7% (n= 189) with NSTEMI, and 8.2% (n
6 = 60) with unstable angina.

7 **Data labeling**

8 The ground truth label distributions across all variables in the ICA dataset were skewed, with
9 varying degrees of class imbalance, ranging from 88% vs 12% for the no CAD label to 33%
10 vs 67% for the occlusion label. As expected, the proportion of patients without CAD was low
11 (12%), as most patients had an occlusion (67%), underwent PCI (75%) and did not have
12 grafts (85%). In the culprit vessel labels, the ramus descendens anterior (RDA), right
13 coronary artery (RCA) and ramus circumflexus (RCx) were the most frequently identified
14 vessels in both the main (361, 211 and 318 times respectively) and subsegment categories
15 (321, 291 and 147 respectively). In contrast, the anterolateral branch (AL) was not annotated
16 in any case and other vessels such as the septal (S) and right ventricular (RV) branches were
17 only rarely identified (both 2 times). A full overview of the label distributions is shown in
18 Appendix

19 Label imbalance in the TTE dataset was even more pronounced. The most frequent class
20 for LV function was “mildly impaired” (52%) whereas “severely impaired” LV function was
21 observed in only 2% of cases. Complete data on LV function were available for all patients.
22 Across all valves, “no dysfunction” was the most common label (83%), followed by
23 “regurgitation” (overall 11%) in all but the pulmonary valve (PV). The PV had the highest
24 proportion of missing data (9%). Notably, no cases of isolated stenosis were recorded for the
25 mitral, tricuspid or pulmonary valves. For valve dysfunction grading, the most common
26 nonnormal category was “mild” (5%) while “moderate” (<1%, 59 cases) and “severe” (<1%,
27 12 cases) grades were uncommon and for mitral stenosis, pulmonary stenosis and
28 pulmonary regurgitation, and entirely absent for tricuspid stenosis. A full overview of the
29 TTE label distributions is provided in Appendix

1 **Annotator agreement**

2 The average agreement between both annotators was high, as shown in Table 2 and 3. In the
3 ICA dataset, accuracy ranged from 0.917 to 0.987, average recall from 0.787 to 0.964 and F1
4 scores from 0.818 to 0.963. The highest scores were observed for graft presence, while the
5 lowest were found in subsegment-level vessel classification. In the TTE dataset, manual
6 annotation scores were consistently high across all labels, with accuracy ranging from 0.993
7 to 1.00, average recall from 0.975 to 1.00 and F1 scores from 0.920 to 1.00. Human
8 performance was particularly strong for binary labels in the ICA dataset and for all TTE
9 labels, while greater variability was observed in more complex and ambiguous tasks such as
10 culprit vessel annotation.

11 **Prompt engineering model assessment**

12 All inputs, combination of prompt and report, were below the context limit and no truncation
13 was encountered. Figure 2 shows the comparison of the 6 selected LLMs for the classification
14 of ICA and TTE reports. The metrics reflect the average classification performance across all
15 labels per report. Results represent the aggregated outcomes from five-fold cross-validation
16 conducted on the training/validation dataset. Original values are 5-fold cross-validation
17 means on training/validation set, see Figures 8-13 in Appendix . For each metric, the mean
18 value and the corresponding 95% confidence interval (CI), derived from 1000 bootstrap
19 samples, are shown. Models run on a local smaller GPU demonstrated slightly inferior
20 performance compared to those trained on a HPC cluster, although the difference was
21 modest. Notably, both the Gemma3 and the Phi4 models showed robust performance in both
22 GPU environments, with the Phi4 model run on the HPC cluster showing best overall
23 performance.

1
 2 Figure 2: Model comparison for prompt engineering on a local machine (16Gb) and on a HPC
 3 cluster (48Gb) for ICA and TTE report classification. For each model the average performance
 4 (of all labels) is shown. 95% CI of metrics calculated with 1000 bootstrapped samples is
 5 indicated with error bars.

6 p[h!]

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2 Figure 3: Model comparison for finetuning on a HPC cluster on ICA and TTE reports. For each
 3 model the average performance (of all labels) is shown. 95% CI of metrics calculated with
 4 1000 bootstrapped samples is indicated with error bars.

5 **Finetune model assessment**

6 For on-site fine-tuning models, context limit was reached in 2% of cases, with no difference
 7 in performance for various truncation methods. For the commercial fine-tuning model no
 8 truncation was encountered. Figure 3 shows the comparison of the 6 selected LLMs for the
 9 classification of ICA and TTE reports. For each model the average performance (of all labels)
 10 is shown. 95% CI of metrics calculated with 1000 bootstrapped samples is indicated with
 11 error bars.. The multilingual model from Intfloat showed best overall performance for
 12 classification of both report types.

13 **Classification results and model comparison**

14 Table 2 and 3 show the performance of the best local prompt engineering and fine-tuning
 15 models compared with prompt engineering and fine-tuning with the commercial model
 16 (GPT-4o) on the held-out test set. The average human annotator performance per task is
 17 shown as an indicator of task difficulty. Per-label counts for the whole dataset are provided
 18 in Supplementary Fig. S1–S4, which contextualize the class imbalance underlying Tables 2
 19 and 3. Especially for the more difficult tasks, GPT-4o showed superior performance for both
 20 prompt engineering and fine-tuning methods and often approaches or surpasses the human
 21 annotator benchmark. For most labels, no statistically significant difference was observed

1 between prompt engineering and fine-tuning when applied to GPT-4o. In contrast,
 2 performance differences were more variable across tasks when using the open-source SOTA
 3 models, while prompt engineering and fine-tuning yielded comparable average performance,
 4 outcomes varied depending on the task. Prompt engineering tended to underperform when
 5 the test set lacked representation of categories included in the prompt. Fine-tuning on the
 6 other hand exhibited diminished performance in severely imbalanced datasets. Complex
 7 tasks such as culprit vessel detection, which are multi-class and multi-label tasks, are
 8 challenging for for all on-site models, regardless of training strategy.

9 **Misclassification analysis**

10 All misclassified labels in the held-out test set of 300 ICA and 300 TTE reports were manually
 11 reviewed to identify recurring patterns and potential sources of model error.

12 **Open source models**

13 For the ICA report classification (Table 2), the fine-tuned model most frequently produced
 14 false negatives for "no CAD" (11/300, 4%), while prompt-engineering yielded a higher false
 15 positive rate (46/300, 15%). Both models over predicted occlusions (13–18%). Graft
 16 detection was generally reliable. However, the fine-tuned model systematically missed
 17 isolated venous grafts (n=9/300, 3%), while prompt-engineering errors were more evenly
 18 distributed. For "Treatment strategy" classification, the fine-tuned model tended to over
 19 predict referral for CABG (n = 5/300, 2%), whereas the prompt-engineered model more often
 20 missed true PCI cases (n = 8/300, 3%). Culprit vessel classification showed notable
 21 limitations. The fine-tuned model only correctly identified 2/24 multi-vessel culprit cases,
 22 this pattern was not observed with prompt-engineering, though its overall accuracy was
 23 inferior in this category. Among main culprit vessel, 16 (5%) errors of fine-tuned model and
 24 26 (9%) errors with prompt engineering were associated to graft-related misclassification.
 25 Notably, prompt engineering failed to assign the "no culprit" label in any case, despite its
 26 presence in 52 test samples. In the sub-vessel category, the fine-tuned model only assigned
 27 the labels RCA, RCx, RDA and no.

28 In TTE reports (Table 3), the fine-tuned model most frequently misclassified mild re-

29 Label	Accuracy	Avg. recall	F1
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Main (manual)	<i>0.943</i>	<i>0.920</i>	<i>0.963</i>
FT (Intfloat)	0.634 [0.580-0.683]	0.392 [0.362-0.42]	0.718 [0.672-0.764]
FT (GPT-4o)	0.870 [0.830-0.907]	0.830 [0.774-0.888]	0.937 [0.914-0.958]
PE (Phi-4)	0.522 [0.467-0.580]	0.510 [0.449-0.579]	0.715 [0.671-0.757]
PE (GPT-4o)	0.761 [0.710-0.803]	0.768 [0.693-0.838]	0.881 [0.849-0.91]
Sub (manual)	<i>0.917</i>	<i>0.787</i>	<i>0.941</i>
FT (Intfloat)	0.533 [0.477-0.587]	0.212 [0.185-0.252]	0.607 [0.554-0.658]
FT (GPT-4o)	0.746 [0.693-0.793]	0.668 [0.576-0.764]	0.819 [0.776-0.857]
PE (Phi-4)	0.460 [0.403-0.520]	0.611 [0.528-0.697]	0.797 [0.761-0.833]
PE (GPT-4o)	0.634 [0.580-0.687]	0.795* [0.719-0.872]	0.830 [0.799-0.862]
No CAD (manual)	<i>0.974</i>	<i>0.964</i>	<i>0.945</i>
FT (Intfloat)	0.960* [0.937-0.980]	0.883 [0.820-0.939]	0.918* [0.867-0.959]
FT (GPT-4o)	0.964* [0.940-0.983]	0.969* [0.940-0.990]	0.936* [0.897-0.971]
PE (Phi-4)	0.974* [0.953-0.990]	0.899 [0.865-0.928]	0.782 [0.727-0.838]
PE (GPT-4o)	0.973* [0.953-0.990]	0.950* [0.904-0.985]	0.949* [0.913-0.979]
Occlusion (manual)	<i>0.926</i>	<i>0.933</i>	<i>0.917</i>
FT (Intfloat)	0.793 [0.750-0.837]	0.752 [0.701-0.801]	0.761 [0.710-0.810]
FT (GPT-4o)	0.920* [0.89-0.947]	0.920* [0.887-0.951]	0.912* [0.878-0.943]
PE (Phi-4)	0.761 [0.713-0.81]	0.697 [0.646-0.752]	0.709 [0.654-0.767]
PE (GPT-4o)	0.927* [0.897-0.953]	0.917* [0.881-0.949]	0.919* [0.884-0.949]
Treatment strategy (manual)	<i>0.976</i>	<i>0.924</i>	<i>0.818</i>
FT (Intfloat)	0.953* [0.930-0.977]	0.895* [0.825-0.955]	0.882* [0.810-0.940]
FT (GPT-4o)	0.987* [0.973-0.997]	0.970* [0.926-0.998]	0.97* [0.931-0.997]
PE (Phi-4)	0.940 [0.910-0.967]	0.835 [0.748-0.917]	0.847* [0.762-0.919]
PE (GPT-4o)	0.977* [0.957-0.993]	0.915* [0.841-0.976]	0.930* [0.868-0.977]
Graft (manual)	<i>0.987</i>	<i>0.940</i>	<i>0.957</i>
FT (Intfloat)	0.970* [0.950-0.987]	0.901* [0.839-0.959]	0.930* [0.881-0.970]
FT (GPT-4o)	0.996* [0.990-1.00]	0.998* [0.994-1.00]	0.992* [0.975-1.00]
PE (Phi-4)	0.993* [0.983-1.00]	0.924* [0.864-0.974]	0.947* [0.905-0.981]
PE (GPT-4o)	0.993* [0.983-1.00]	0.996* [0.990-1.00]	0.986* [0.965-1.00]

1 Table 2: Model comparison for ICA report classification on the test set. Four LLM models and
2 training methods are compared on 6 labels extracted from ICA reports. Comparison is done
3 with 3 metrics: accuracy, average recall and F1. The 95% CI is given in brackets. The best
4 metric score and any score that is not significantly different from this score ($p_b=0.0167$), is
5 indicated with bold font. Manual annotation scores are averaged human annotator scores
6 and are shown in *italic*. Significant improvement or equality to the manual score is indicated
7 with an asterisk (*). FT = fine-tuning, PE = prompt engineering.

1

Label	Accuracy	Avg. recall	F1
LV function (manual)	<i>0.997</i>	<i>0.998</i>	<i>0.998</i>
FT (Intfloat)	0.984* [0.967-0.997]	0.918 [0.809-0.988]	0.947 [0.869-0.993]
FT (GPT-4o)	1.00* [1.00-1.00]	1.00* [1.00-1.00]	1.00* [1.00-1.00]
PE (Phi-4)	0.727 [0.667-0.777]	0.805 [0.753-0.849]	0.518 [0.429-0.647]
PE (GPT-4o)	0.997* [0.990-1.00]	0.998* [0.995-1.00]	0.993* [0.976-1.00]
Mitral Sten. Grade (manual)	<i>1.00</i>	<i>1.00</i>	<i>1.00</i>
FT (Intfloat)	0.969 [0.950-0.987]	0.555 [0.495-0.667]	0.578 [0.488-0.745]
FT (GPT-4o)	0.997* [0.990-1.00]	0.998* [0.995-1.00]	0.972* [0.897-1.00]
PE (Phi-4)	0.796 [0.750-0.837]	0.410 [0.388-0.431]	0.223 [0.215-0.229]
PE (GPT-4o)	1.00* [1.00-1.00]	1.00* [1.00-1.00]	1.00* [1.00-1.00]
Mitral Reg. grade (manual)	<i>0.997</i>	<i>0.975</i>	<i>0.920</i>
FT (Intfloat)	0.866 [0.827-0.903]	0.372 [0.298-0.475]	0.379 [0.295-0.504]
FT (GPT-4o)	0.990* [0.977-1.00]	0.963* [0.900-1.00]	0.896* [0.738-1.00]
PE (Phi-4)	0.893 [0.860-0.927]	0.783 [0.688-0.869]	0.707 [0.532-0.853]
PE (GPT-4o)	0.980 [0.963-0.993]	0.946* [0.878-0.989]	0.897* [0.743-0.993]
Aortic Sten. grade (manual)	<i>1.00</i>	<i>1.00</i>	<i>1.00</i>
FT (Intfloat)	0.907 [0.873-0.940]	0.219 [0.200-0.250]	0.208 [0.187-0.242]
FT (GPT-4o)	0.997* [0.987-1.00]	0.999* [0.997-1.00]	0.991* [0.968-1.00]
PE (Phi-4)	0.866 [0.823-0.903]	0.791 [0.721-0.850]	0.516 [0.377-0.665]
PE (GPT-4o)	0.990* [0.977-1.00]	0.856* [0.753-1.00]	0.836* [0.712-1.00]
Aortic Reg. grade (manual)	<i>0.993</i>	<i>0.984</i>	<i>0.991</i>
FT (Intfloat)	0.843 [0.800-0.883]	0.201 [0.200-0.201]	0.184 [0.178-0.19]
FT (GPT-4o)	0.987* [0.973-0.997]	0.975* [0.948-0.999]	0.978* [0.952-0.996]
PE (Phi-4)	0.876 [0.837-0.913]	0.795 [0.772-0.834]	0.661 [0.553-0.744]
PE (GPT-4o)	0.973 [0.953-0.990]	0.885 [0.751-0.967]	0.904 [0.742-0.980]
Tricuspid Sten. grade (manual)	<i>0.993</i>	<i>0.997</i>	<i>0.957</i>
FT (Intfloat)	0.963 [0.94-0.983]	0.500 [0.500-0.500]	0.491 [0.485-0.496]
FT (GPT-4o)	0.967 [0.947-0.987]	0.983 [0.972-0.993]	0.831 [0.727-0.925]
PE (Phi-4)	0.838 [0.793-0.877]	0.435 [0.415-0.454]	0.185 [0.177-0.229]
PE (GPT-4o)	0.997* [0.990-1.00]	0.998* [0.995-1.00]	0.977* [0.913-1.00]
Tricuspid Reg. grade (manual)	<i>0.993</i>	<i>0.998</i>	<i>0.978</i>
FT (Intfloat)	0.887 [0.850-0.923]	0.260 [0.250-0.333]	0.245 [0.230-0.317]
FT (GPT-4o)	0.963 [0.943-0.983]	0.978 [0.947-0.994]	0.905 [0.841-0.955]
PE (Phi-4)	0.853 [0.81-0.893]	0.797 [0.702-0.878]	0.491 [0.360-0.657]
PE (GPT-4o)	0.980* [0.963-0.993]	0.961 [0.912-0.997]	0.901* [0.701-0.985]
Pulmonary Sten. grade (manual)	<i>0.997</i>	<i>0.998</i>	<i>0.991</i>
FT (Intfloat)	0.987* [0.973-0.997]	0.950* [0.896-0.998]	0.963* [0.926-0.992]
FT (GPT-4o)	0.993* [0.983-1.00]	0.982* [0.945-1.00]	0.982* [0.950-1.00]
PE (Phi-4)	0.834 [0.790-0.877]	0.508 [0.459-0.568]	0.260 [0.191-0.384]
PE (GPT-4o)	0.996* [0.987-1.00]	0.998* [0.993-1.00]	0.990* [0.967-1.00]
Pulmonary Reg. grade (manual)	<i>0.997</i>	<i>0.999</i>	<i>0.994</i>
FT (Intfloat)	0.963 [0.940-0.983]	0.634 [0.597-0.665]	0.638 [0.612-0.659]
FT (GPT-4o)	0.990* [0.977-1.0]	0.939* [0.820-1.00]	0.958* [0.873-1.00]
PE (Phi-4)	0.816 [0.770-0.860]	0.740 [0.684-0.800]	0.427 [0.349-0.507]

PE (GPT-4o)	0.993* [0.983-1.00]	0.950* [0.831-1.00]	0.964* [0.876-1.00]
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1 Table 3: Model comparison for TTE report classification on the test set. Four LLM models and
 2 training methods are compared on 9 labels extracted from TTE reports. Comparison is done
 3 with 3 metrics: accuracy, average recall and F1. The 95% CI is given in brackets. The best
 4 metric score and any score that is not significantly different from this score ($p_b=0.0167$), is
 5 indicated with bold font. Manual annotation scores are averaged human observer scores and
 6 are shown in *italic*. Significant improvement or equality to this manual score is indicated
 7 with an asterisk (*). FT = fine-tuning, PE = prompt engineering.

8
 9 gurgitation as none (AV: n = 25/300, 8%; MV: n = 14/300, 5%). In contrast, prompt
 10 engineering occasionally overestimated pathology, predicting dysfunction where none was
 11 present. Stenosis grading errors followed similar patterns, with the fine-tuned model under-
 12 calling and prompt-engineering over-calling severity. Notably, the fine-tuned model assigned
 13 the "no dysfunction" label to the AV in all cases.

14 **Commercial models**

15 For commercial models (Table 2), both prompt-engineering and fine-tuning showed the
 16 lowest performance for culprit vessel classification. Prompt-engineering produced 24% and
 17 the finetuned model 13% main vessel labeling errors. Common issues included labeling both
 18 main and sub-branches (15% and 12%, respectively), and misclassifying graft versus native
 19 vessels. Both models consistently failed to recognize the IM branch correctly (3/9 cases
 20 each). Errors in classifying the presence of acute occlusions were often related to the
 21 presence of CTOs and grafts. Misclassifications also occurred in differentiating pre-existing
 22 CTOs from new obstructive disease. In both approaches, the most common misclassifications
 23 for the labels graft, no CAD and occlusion were false positives. With the prompt engineering
 24 method, these occurred in 2/300 (1%), 6/300 (2%) and 19/300 (6%) cases, respectively,
 25 whereas with the fine-tuned model, the corresponding rates were 1/300 (<1%), 10/300
 26 (3%), and 6/300 (2%). For "treatment strategy" classification, the most common error in
 27 both models was predicting medical therapy only while a referral for CABG was mentioned,
 28 particularly in reports indicating pending diagnostics (prompt engineering: n=5/300, 2%;
 29 fine-tuned model: n=2/300, 1%).

1 In TTE data (Table 3), valvular assessment was the main challenge, particularly
2 differentiating between "none" and "no data" due to inconsistencies between structured data
3 and narrative conclusions. For example, cases where mild MR was quantitatively reported
4 but summarized as "no dysfunction" in the narrative conclusion. Additional errors were
5 linked to ambiguous or non-diagnostic phrases, such as "TV: TR gradient 30 mmHg" or "AV
6 opens well visually, no reliable gradient". Both models under predicted mild regurgitation,
7 with the fine-tuned model showing fewer errors overall. LV function classification was
8 accurate, with only isolated errors.

9 Discussion

10 LLM-based methods are a very valuable tool in the automation of ICA and TTE report
11 classification. Depending on the accuracy required, the labeling difficulty and the available
12 budget and computational power, different LLM-based methods can be used for the
13 automation of report classification.

14 In this study, the performance of LLMs using both prompt engineering and fine-tuning
15 was evaluated for the classification of TTE and ICA reports across different computational
16 environments: i. a local server, ii. a HPC cluster and iii. a commercial cloud-based API (e.g.,
17 GPT-4o). The goal was to explore the practical feasibility, performance and trade-offs for
18 different LLM approaches in processing real-world cardiology data.

19 **Model performance and comparative analysis** Across platforms, LLMs demonstrated
20 robust performance in classifying key clinical findings with minimal pre-processing,
21 underscoring their potential integration into cardiology workflows such as automated EHR
22 annotation, registry data generation and retrospective data structuring. Compared with
23 manual annotation by a single experienced reviewer, GPT-4o-based approaches
24 demonstrated similar performance for most tasks, except for culprit vessel identification, the
25 most complex task, and tricuspid regurgitation grading with the finetuning approach, where
26 severe class imbalance impaired model performance. Open-source models exhibited similar
27 task-specific performance trends but with consistently lower accuracy. For simpler tasks
28 with balanced classes, both modeling approaches performed comparable to the human
29 annotator. The lowest performance was observed in tasks involving both main and sub-

1 culprit vessel identification, consistent with the inherent complexity of the task. Additionally,
2 the strict evaluation criterion for these tasks contribute to lower performance metrics. In the
3 context of TTE reports, classification errors often resulted from inconsistencies between
4 structured quantitative measurements and the narrative conclusions. For example, cases
5 describing mild mitral regurgitation in the measurements section were occasionally
6 summarized in the conclusion as “no dysfunction”. Furthermore, the presence of clinically
7 benign phrases, such as “calcified annulus with normal function”, occasionally triggered
8 false-positive classifications. The various approaches revealed different levels of task
9 comprehension, likely influenced by model architecture and scale²³. For instance, the
10 prompt-engineered open-source model frequently labeled any vessel with atherosclerotic
11 plaque as a culprit lesion, without adequately considering the degree of luminal narrowing,
12 indicating limitations in nuanced clinical reasoning. Importantly, GPT-4o achieved high and
13 consistent performance across both prompt-based and fine-tuned implementations.
14 However, fine-tuning required significantly greater computational resources, a larger volume
15 of annotated training data and incurred substantially higher monetary costs. These trade-
16 offs suggest that for many clinical applications, particularly in resource-constrained
17 environments, prompt engineering with commercial models offers a more pragmatic and
18 scalable solution. Conversely, in complex tasks such as culprit vessel labeling, fine-tuning
19 appeared to meaningfully enhance performance, supporting its use where feasible. While
20 locally deployed open-source models did not match GPT-4o’s performance in complex
21 classification tasks, they remain valuable in settings with simpler classification needs,
22 stricter data privacy constraints, or limited budgets. These models provide a viable
23 alternative for institutions that prefer not to rely on third-party cloud-based services.

24 **Prompt engineering vs. fine-tuning** A notable observation in our analysis was that smaller
25 fine-tuned models achieved performance comparable to larger prompt-engineered models
26 on several classification tasks. This aligns with findings from prior computational research,
27 which suggest that, while fine-tuning allows for task-specific adaptation, its benefits may be
28 constrained by the underlying model capacity.²⁴ Conversely, larger prompt engineered
29 models can leverage broad pre-trained knowledge and perform well without full retraining.
30 These results support a balanced interpretation: a more targeted learning strategy (fine-
31 tuning) applied to a smaller model may yield comparable results to a less customized

1 strategy (prompt engineering) implemented with a larger model. Additionally, it was shown
2 that fine-tuning is more susceptible to class imbalance, which can lead to overfitting if not
3 properly mitigated. This was particularly evident in the fine-tuned open-source model, which
4 learned to classify all aortic valves as non-dysfunctional; a result that maximized
5 performance on the imbalanced training set but failed to generalize. However, this holds true
6 for all use cases with highly imbalanced data. In comparison, prompt-engineered approaches
7 demonstrated greater resilience to label sparsity, suggesting an advantage in scenarios with
8 limited or unevenly distributed annotations. From a practical perspective, this trade-off
9 highlights the importance of aligning methodological choices with both task complexity and
10 available infrastructure. While fine-tuning offers the potential for precise task optimization,
11 it demands considerable computational resources, annotated training data and technical
12 expertise. In contrast, prompt engineering, particularly when applied to large-scale
13 foundation models, offers a more accessible and scalable alternative, especially in structured
14 domains such as diagnostic and procedural cardiology reporting.

15 The dataset used for training and evaluation reflects a typical ACS population,
16 representative both in patient characteristics and disease distribution.[?] This real-world
17 alignment enhances the external validity of our findings. However, as a consequence the
18 dataset exhibits substantial class imbalance, mirroring the natural prevalence of clinical
19 findings in ACS, which poses challenges for model training, particularly for fine-tuning
20 strategies. While prompt-based approaches can partially mitigate these effects through
21 tailored task formulations, fine-tuned models remain more susceptible to underperformance
22 in underrepresented classes.

23 **Limitations and generalizability** Furthermore, overall human annotator scores were high,
24 but lower for more complex labels such as culprit vessel and occlusion, likely due to the
25 ambiguous and complex nature of these annotations. During ICA procedures, the culprit
26 lesion may not be unequivocally identified, particularly in cases of NSTEMI, multivessel
27 disease or diffuse atherosclerosis²⁵. Labeling sub-branches of the culprit vessel was even
28 more ambiguous, due to complex anatomical relations and lesions affecting multiple
29 branches at the same time. These ambiguities, exacerbated by the multi-class and multilabel
30 nature of vessel-related classifications, make for highly complex classification tasks.

1 Additionally, a notable proportion of the dataset included patients with prior CABG or CTOs,
2 introducing further anatomical variation and interpretation challenges.

3 To isolate model performance from labeling effort, we fixed the labeled dataset size
4 across models and did not rebalance the dataset, which keeps implementation burden
5 comparable but leaves some label categories with limited representation. In applied settings,
6 rare labels may be enriched via keyword screening to prioritize these cases.

7 This study primarily focused on moderately structured clinical text, due to the
8 procedural nature of analyzed reports, which typically contain more templated or semi-
9 standardized phrasing. Extending these methods to unstructured clinical narratives, such as
10 clinical rounding notes or discharge summaries, will likely pose greater challenges due to
11 their variability and contextual complexity. Nonetheless, reports used in this analysis were
12 created by numerous different cardiologists, introducing heterogeneity in structure and
13 phrasing.

14 We anticipate that similar LLM-based strategies can effectively be extended to less
15 structured clinical text, provided that more extensive prompt engineering and carefully
16 defined output schemas are employed to handle the greater variability. Moreover, while our
17 datasets were sourced from a single academic institution, the underlying LLM-based
18 approaches are inherently portable. They can be adapted to local data environments,
19 allowing for institution-specific customization while leveraging generalizable architectures
20 and workflows. Nevertheless, our comparisons were limited to single-center datasets;
21 extending these methods across multiple institutions may alter performance, as the benefits
22 of fine-tuning could be reduced. Additionally, because we did not formally map outputs to
23 standardized terminologies such as SNOMED CT, cross-institution interoperability remains
24 to be established.

25 **Future Directions** Future research should prioritize the development of advanced prompt
26 optimization strategies, including automated prompt generation and hybrid frameworks
27 that integrate prompt engineering with minimal fine-tuning. These approaches may offer a
28 more efficient balance between performance and resource demands, particularly in settings
29 with limited annotated data. In addition, performance could be further enhanced by

1 incorporating post-processing techniques, such as rule-based corrections or ensemble
2 methods, that aggregate outputs from multiple models to enhance reliability. Guideline-
3 grounded prompting and retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) may be explored to surface
4 the most relevant guideline passages at inference time. When combined with schema-
5 constrained outputs and simple rule-based adjudication, guideline-based diagnoses could be
6 derived from free-text reports while maintaining transparency and ease of update.

7 The application of LLM-based data extraction to less structured clinical texts, such as
8 progress notes and discharge summaries, warrants further investigation, as these sources
9 contain rich contextual information but pose greater linguistic and structural challenges.
10 Another interesting direction is applying LLMs to map free-text reports directly to
11 standardized terminologies to streamline multi-institution data aggregation and enable joint
12 analyses with minimal additional conversion steps.

13 Given the rapid evolution of LLM architectures and hardware, with new models
14 showing both similar performance with a lower parameter count and superior
15 performance with similar or higher parameter counts, we anticipate continuous
16 improvement in performance, accessibility and applicability in clinical cardiology
17 settings.²⁶

18 **Conclusion** In conclusion, both fine-tuning and prompt engineering approaches to LLMs
19 offer valuable tools for the structured classification of cardiology reports. Prompt
20 engineering provides a lightweight, adaptable and cost-efficient strategy, particularly
21 suitable for low-resource settings. Fine-tuning, while resource-intensive, enables more
22 targeted optimization. While commercial LLMs generally outperform open-source models in
23 challenging classification tasks, locally deployed models achieved good performance for
24 more structured or narrowly defined applications. The choice between approaches should
25 be guided by the clinical use case, available infrastructure, local expertise and regulatory or
26 privacy considerations. Critically, the traditional bottleneck of manual data labeling is rapidly
27 becoming obsolete. With LLMs now capable of accurate, scalable information extraction from
28 raw clinical text, the development of machine learning pipelines no longer hinges on large
29 annotated datasets. This shift unlocks new opportunities for rapid deployment of AI in

1 cardiology, from real-time decision support to large-scale data curation. As the technology
2 continues to evolve, LLMs are set to become foundational infrastructure for cardiovascular
3 research and clinical practice alike.

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8 **Disclosures**

9 None

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Graphical Abstract
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